

IMPROVING NETWORK SECURITY IN SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED BUSINESSES THROUGH LOG ANALYSIS USING ELK

*A.M.A.P Amarasinghe**

Post Graduate Student, Faculty of Computing, Sri Lanka Institute of Information Technology, Malabe, Sri Lanka.

**Corresponding Author*

E-Mail Id:- ms21928024@my.sliit.lk

ABSTRACT

The administration of a company's security measures is a crucial responsibility. A simple method for detecting and avoiding cyberattacks may be found in today's security information and event management (SIEM) systems. Small firms can't afford commercial SIEM solutions, and their performance expectations won't be reached. To build a cost-free SIEM solution, support for the ELK stack (an acronym for three open-source projects) will be provided. Our findings suggest that it may be beneficial to use a more suitable SIEM solution for a typical activity, both from a performance and productivity standpoint.

Keywords:- *Elasticsearch, Logstash, Kibana, SIEM*

INTRODUCTION

Cyber security, computer security, or information technology security refers to the protection of computers, servers, electronic systems, mobile devices, data, and networks against potential security threats [2,14]. Cybersecurity risks have become a major concern for contemporary enterprises, which cannot be managed by focusing just on computer security, network security, or software security [9]. However, developments in each of these areas would result in a reduction of the hazards to a certain extent. SIEM is a critical solution for identifying most network device assaults and correlating data from firewalls, routers, AVs, ADs, DLPs, and other devices [1,2]. There are several SIEMs to choose from, each with its own unique architecture and set of

capabilities. The high cost of commercial SIEMs systems is a significant barrier to entry for small and medium-sized businesses [13]. For this reason, the creation of a free, high-performance SIEM solution is essential.

By providing a centralized location for data collection, storage, analysis, and visualization, Elastic Stack (ELK stack) serves as a foundation upon which SIEM solutions may be built. Elastic is the firm responsible for managing and maintaining the ELK stack. Elastic search, Logstash, and Kibana are all acronyms. Elasticsearch is an advanced analytics and search platform. Kibana is a data visualization engine, while Logstash is a data processing pipeline. The performance of log analysis in comparison to commercial solutions is a significant area of

study, since ELK stack represents a promising option for small and medium-sized businesses. It would be beneficial to create ELK-based SIEM as a flexible SIEM option for small and medium-sized businesses. The ELK stack will also be used to create a SIEM solution for use in the cloud, with the aim of selling it to customers as a managed service [6,7].

The remaining sections of this work are structured as follows. We then describe our methodology and literature review. After that, the Necessary Resources and Feasibility will be outlined. The report ends with a conclusion and suggestions for further research.

LITERATURE SURVEY

When thinking about the Security Operation Center (SOC) environment, Security Information and Event Management Systems (SIEM) solutions play a crucial role for identify and react to security issues. [16]

Overview of SIEM

The term "Security Information and Event Management" (SIEM) refers to the merging of these two concepts. The information gathered by SIM may be stored in one convenient location, and reports and regulatory compliance can be managed with ease. In order to effectively take defensive measures by security professionals, SEM analyzes the collected data and gives the capability of identifying security events in real time. [3]

SIEM systems often include a behavior profiling component. During the pattern-learning phase, this will recognize each user's patterns, and if their conduct deviates from the usual, it will trigger events or alerts according to the rules set up. A SIEM's log

management and reporting capabilities are also crucial. The SIEM system will be responsible for the logging process from beginning to end, including data storage, analysis, indexing, search, and report production. Most SIEM systems provide both pre-defined and ad hoc report production capabilities in their reporting features.

Figure 1 depicts the generalized architecture of a SIEM system.

Figure 1:-Overview of SIEM Workflow Architecture

Intelligence on Cyber Threats from Honeypot Data

Intelligence about potential cyber threats is crucial for businesses looking to protect themselves against hacking. One very efficient strategy for detecting cyberattacks is to create a client Honeypot and collect data from it. When used correctly, a honeypot may foil the efforts of several attackers at once. These Honey pot data sets are used by many researchers as a foundation for their threat hunting operations. When analyzing Indicators of Compromise (IoC) and using the resulting data to guide the identification of attack scenarios in a Honeypot setting, Binaco's Pyramid of Pain (PoP) will be handy. There are three criteria that may be

used to assess each IoC. Throttle, identifying information, and the Trace system. Different traces are available to identify an attacker's entry into an organization, such as their IP address, hash, attack tools, attack methodologies (network scan, port scan, etc.), etc. Honeypot data will be easier to analyze and see with the help of ELK stack's streamlined environment. [8,10]

Overview of ELK Stack

Elasticsearch, Logstash, and Kibana are the initials for three separate open source initiatives. Elasticsearch's design philosophy centers on a robust REST API and the use of JSON for data transit. Elasticsearch indexes documents in JSON and conducts real-time searches across massive amounts of data. [6]

Logstash is a data processing pipeline that runs on a server and moves information to a storage system. Logstash's primary function is to collect data from a variety of log sources, alter it as necessary, and then forward it to Elasticsearch. There are three major components to Logstash. The inputs, filters, and outputs make up the system. The input indicates the source from which logs are being read, the filter the destination to which the data must be filtered before being stored.

Kibana is a tool for displaying and analyzing data. Kibana can collect data from Elasticsearch and display it in a variety of graphical and tabular forms for analysis. This Kibana engine is built on top of well-developed APIs. [7]

Overview of Log Management System

Organizations need a Log Management System in order to detect malicious activity, perform forensic investigations, and meet

regulatory standards. The difficult element is gathering relevant data and real-time risk-rated identification of suspicious situations.[1] The Log Management System's (LMS) primary role is to gather logs and classify them into different categories according to their severity. The majority of network nodes can provide Syslog data to an LMS server.

97% of companies keep logs, and 42% of those companies submit them to a security information and event management system, according to a recent study of 522 businesses. Of these businesses, 22% are struggling with log correlation, and 14% are having trouble classifying and normalizing their logs [2]. The LMS has to be able to parse the various log formats coming into it, and efficient data pre-processing is essential for fixing these problems. Thus, it is crucial to manage logs effectively in order to preserve visibility across networks, applications, and systems. One study from recently [2] recommends an 11-step process for implementing a log management infrastructure in an environment with plenty of other servers. The first thing to do is to identify what needs to be done. The security policy, use cases, risk analysis, legal advice, and validation of incidents as well as any relevant laws or standards are outlined. The rules that apply will be different for each jurisdiction and kind of business. When collecting logs, companies should think about their security policies and how to protect people's personal information. To determine the criticality and relevance of logging for each system, further risk evaluation of each asset is necessary. The following stage, after compiling the list of logging requirements, is to catalog the hardware and software in use inside the company. At this point, it will detail the

servers, PCs, network infrastructure devices, scanners, printers, mobile devices, etc. in use throughout the firm, as well as the software installed on each. The next action is to create a topology diagram of the network. The network connections of each device will be clear when this diagram is drawn, and you'll have a clear route to collecting log data. In certain cases, it may be necessary to gather data from completely isolated devices if they are included in the network topology diagram. The next thing to do is decide what data to record. The next step is to determine the logging level that will be enabled; this is important since it affects the requirements for the network and the storage space. Log levels must be defined according to organizational policy, legal requirements, and investigative needs. Choose the system architecture on the fifth level. The log management infrastructure will be established at this stage based on the needs identified at the previous stages, the organization's objectives, anticipated future needs, and the available resources. Hardware, software, storage, way of dumping log data, and network improvement type things will all be chosen in this infrastructure. The LMS's top-level architecture, which may be centralized or decentralized, unified or fragmented, and special or standard, will also be specified.

Overview of LogRhythm SIEM

For security analytics, you may rely on LogRhythm, a commercial SIEM product. Various data analysis tools are included. The data processor will handle data, the data indexer will create indexes, and Netmon will perform network packet analysis. The artificial intelligence engine will detect various risks. Logrhythm also benefits from having UBEA capabilities, which stands for User and Entity Behavior Analytics. UBEA

indicates that a SIEM system will first detect each user's activity in a normal setting, and then alerts will be triggered depending on anomalous behavior.

METHODOLOGY

One promising subject for further study, as determined by an examination of the relevant literature, is the commercial assessment of the performance of log analysis software developed using the ELK stack [13]. In addition, a SIEM as a managed service will be made available to users of this experimental model.

Choose SIEM Systems for Analysis

There are number of SIEM solutions available in the market. As per the Gartner report of 2020, Figure 2 evaluates different SIEM systems [11,12].

Figure.2:-Magic Quadrant for SIEM

Case Study for Analyses

The visualization methods and assessment standards used by SIEM systems vary. This experimental setup will test the commercial SIEM systems' threat analysis, performance, and visualization methods to see how well they measure up to the experimental setup's standards. In this setting, considering the case

studies down below, Situational awareness is the ability to recognize potential dangers Identifying threats in real time Visualizing potential dangers in a variety of situations Possibility to specify search criteria Ability to improve effectiveness while seeking and assessing several potential threat situations.

Research Methodology

In this method, we use an ELK stack environment hosted in the cloud for logging and analysis purposes. The logs may be automatically uploaded or fed from distant places. The information stored in the ELK stack will reveal the nature of the attacks, any vulnerabilities, and any potentially unusual communication patterns. Figure 3 shows a high-level diagram of the design.

Figure 3: Cloud-based ELK stack experiment setup.

As can be seen in Figure 3, the ELK server will be housed in the cloud, and all network-related traffic and logs will be sent there. Logstash, housed inside the ELK server, will

filter, map, and store filtered logs in Elasticsearch based on parameters you provide. These analyzed logs may be accessed using the Kibana tool. Kibana interfaces will allow users to see how their networks are really behaving in real time. Attracting malevolent agents using a T-Pot honeypot system is only one of many possible applications for this setup, since the resulting traffic may be analyzed for insights about the nature of the attackers and the attacks they intend to perform against an organization's internal network. T-Pot will allow the company to deploy multipurpose honeypot settings, and the resulting data will make security flaws in the existing system clear. In addition, this arrangement will be hosted in the cloud environment, since doing so will make it easier to analyze network data from a variety of organizations and point the way toward making this configuration more suitable for offering a SIEM as a managed service.

FEASIBILITY AND FACILITIES REQUIRED

There is no cost to use Elasticsearch, Logstash, or Kibana. The ELK stack environment may be deployed to the cloud with the creation of a suitable cloud account, such as one on Azure or Amazon. Improved server hardware infrastructure can be quickly implemented in a cloud setting. The system's performance will be much improved compared to what is already in place. Honeypot software is free and open source. Honeypot data and network traffic collected locally may be sent to the cloud, or data sets can be uploaded directly to the cloud. Local installation is an option if a sufficient amount of bandwidth cannot be guaranteed through the network. Both the experimental setup and the commercial program called LogRhythm

may use the same data collection or network traffic for performance analysis. There are performance assessment queries that may be executed in either setting for the sake of analysis.

CONCLUSION AND FURTHER WORKS

Implement of log analyzing mechanism is very important due to prevailing and emerging cyber threats. The commercial safeguard SIEM tools critical gaps found when implementing to the small and medium scale business environments. This will cut the concern of SIEM implementation cost and will provide an effective log analyzing mechanism for small and medium scale companies. ELK stack provides similar or better performance when compared with commercial SIEM tools for small, medium scale companies. Further ELK provide various kind of customizable visualization capabilities which will useful for security administrators. ELK provides a powerful beginning for small and medium-scale companies.

Log analysis performance, autonomous response features, and AI engine capabilities are all areas that might benefit from further investigation and development in the ELK environment. This infrastructure has the potential to evolve into a software framework [15] that can efficiently analyze the logs of large-scale businesses.

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